

The Effect of Intranasal Olopatadine Hydrochloride on Influenza A and B Symptoms In Children: A Clinical Observation and Comparative Evaluation

İntranasal Olopatadin Hidroklorür'ün Çocuklarda İnfluenza A ve B Semptomlarına Etkisi: Klinik Gözlem ve Karşılaştırmalı Değerlendirme

Vefik Arıca¹, Taner Adıgüzel²

¹University of Health Sciences, İstanbul Prof. Dr. Cemil Taşcıoğlu City Hospital, Department of Pediatrics, İstanbul, Türkiye

²Yalova University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pediatrics, Yalova, Türkiye

ABSTRACT

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the effects of intranasal Olopatadine Hydrochloride on nasal and systemic symptoms in pediatric patients diagnosed with influenza A or B infection.

Material and Method: Children aged 6-18 years who presented to the Pediatric Outpatient Clinics of Health Sciences University Prof. Dr. Cemil Taşcıoğlu City Hospital and Yalova Training and Research Hospital between 1 January and 15 March 2025 and were diagnosed with influenza A or B were retrospectively evaluated. Patients (n=50) who received appropriately dosed intranasal Olopatadine Hydrochloride alongside symptomatic treatment underwent face-to-face interviews regarding their previous treatment experience, including symptom profiles and duration.

Results: In the influenza A-positive group (n=25), the duration of nasal congestion was 2 days in the group receiving intranasal Olopatadine Hydrochloride (n=13) versus 6 days in the group receiving no Olopatadine Hydrochloride (n=12). Sneezing lasted 1 day in the Olopatadine group and 7 days in the group receiving no Olopatadine. No significant differences were observed in systemic symptoms. A significant reduction in the duration of nasal congestion and sneezing was observed in the Olopatadine group (p < 0.001). In the influenza B-positive group (n=25), nasal congestion lasted 1 day in the Olopatadine group (n=13) and 3 days in the other group (n=12). Sneezing lasted 1 day in the Olopatadine group and 4 days in the other. Again, there were no significant differences in systemic symptoms. A significant reduction in nasal congestion and sneezing duration was observed in the Olopatadine group (p<0.01). Among the patients with concurrent influenza A and B infection (n=5), nasal congestion lasted 1 day in those treated with Olopatadine (n=3) compared to 6 days in the other group (n=2). Sneezing lasted 1 day in the Olopatadine group and 5 days in the other. No significant difference was found in systemic symptoms. However, there was a significant reduction in nasal congestion and sneezing duration in the Olopatadine group (p<0.001).

Conclusion: Intranasal Olopatadine may significantly reduce nasal symptoms in children with influenza A and B infections.

Keywords: Influenza, Olopatadine Hydrochloride, nasal congestion, sneeze

ÖZ

Amaç: Bu çalışmada, İnfluenza A ve B enfeksiyonu tanısı almış çocuk hastalarda intranasal Olopatadin Hidroklorür kullanımının nazal ve sistemik semptomlar üzerindeki etkileri değerlendirilmiştir.

Gereç ve Yöntem: 1 Ocak-15 Mart 2025 tarihleri arasında Sağlık Bilimleri Üniversitesi Prof. Dr. Cemil Taşcıoğlu Şehir Hastanesi Çocuk Polikliniğine ve Yalova Eğitim ve Araştırma Hastanesi Çocuk Polikliniğine başvuran ve influenza A/B tanısı alan 6-18 yaş aralığındaki çocuklara semptomatik tedavileri yanında intranasal olopatadin hidroklorür uygun dozda başlanan hastalara (n=50) geçmişe yönelik tedavilerine yönelik yüzyüze görüşme sağlandı ve o dönemki semptomları, kaç gün sürdüğüne dair veriler alındı.

Bulgular: İnfluenza A pozitif hasta grubunda (n=25); nazal konjesyon süresi İntranasal Olopatadin Hidroklorür alan grupta (n=13) 2 gün, almayan grupta (n=12) 6 gün idi. Hapşırık süresi ise İntranasal Olopatadin Hidroklorür alan grupta 1 gün, almayan grupta 7 gün idi. Sistemik semptomlarda anlamlı fark izlenmedi. İnfluenza A pozitif olguların Olopatadin grubunda nazal konjesyon ve hapşırık süresinde anlamlı azalma gözlemlendi (p < 0.001). İnfluenza B pozitif hasta grubunda (n=25); nazal konjesyon süresi İntranasal Olopatadin Hidroklorür alan grupta (n=13) 1 gün, almayan grupta (n=12) 3 gün idi. Hapşırık süresi ise İntranasal Olopatadin Hidroklorür alan grupta 1 gün, almayan grupta 4 gün idi. Sistemik semptomlarda anlamlı fark izlenmedi. İnfluenza B pozitif olguların Olopatadin grubunda nazal konjesyon ve hapşırık süresinde anlamlı azalma gözlemlendi (p < 0.01). İnfluenza A ve B pozitif hasta grubunda (n=5); nazal konjesyon süresi İntranasal Olopatadin Hidroklorür alan grupta (n=3) 1 gün, almayan grupta (n=2) 6 gün idi. Hapşırık süresi ise İntranasal Olopatadin Hidroklorür alan grupta 1 gün, almayan grupta 5 gün idi. Sistemik semptomlarda anlamlı fark izlenmedi. Olopatadin grubunda nazal konjesyon ve hapşırık süresinde anlamlı azalma gözlemlendi (p<0.001).

Sonuç: İntranasal Olopatadin, İnfluenza A ve B enfeksiyonu geçiren çocuklarda nazal semptomları anlamlı şekilde azaltabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İnfluenza, Olopatadin Hidroklorür, nazal konjesyon, hapşırık

Corresponding Author: Vefik Arıca

Address: University of Health Sciences, İstanbul Prof. Dr. Cemil Taşcıoğlu City Hospital, Department of Pediatrics, İstanbul, Türkiye

E-mail: vefikarica@hotmail.com

Başvuru Tarihi/Received: 20.05.2025

Kabul Tarihi/Accepted: 25.06.2025

INTRODUCTION

The influenza virus is a major cause of upper respiratory tract infections in children. In particular, Influenza A and B strains lead to high morbidity among school-aged children (1). Symptoms like nasal congestion and sneezing not only increase the risk of transmission but also reduce the quality of life (2).

There are scientific data indicating the use of Olopatadine Hydrochloride in the treatment of allergic rhinitis and seasonal allergic rhinitis. However, the data supporting its efficacy in alleviating nasal congestion and discharge due to upper respiratory tract infections are limited (3,4).

Olopatadine Hydrochloride has inhibitory effects on the release of inflammatory lipid mediators like leukotrienes and thromboxanes from polymorphonuclear leukocytes and eosinophils (5). Studies involving healthy volunteers revealed that Olopatadine is highly absorbed, with approximately 58% excreted via urine and minimal involvement of metabolism in its elimination (6).

Olopatadine Hydrochloride exhibits H1 antihistaminergic and mast stabilizing effects. Its anti-inflammatory and antiallergic properties were reported in the literature (7-12).

Olopatadine is an FDA-approved intranasal antihistamine indicated for the treatment of allergic rhinitis (13).

This study aimed to investigate the effect of the second-generation H1 receptor antagonist Olopatadine on nasal symptoms associated with influenza infections.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study was approved by Yalova University's Clinical Research Ethics Committee (Date: 06.01.2025, Decision No: 2025/04). The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Patient confidentiality and personal data were protected.

Patients who presented to the Pediatric Outpatient Clinics of Prof. Dr. Cemil Taşcıoğlu City Hospital of Health Sciences University and Yalova Training and Research Hospital and were diagnosed with influenza A/B between 1 January and 15 March 2025 were included in this study.

This prospective observational study enrolled 50 pediatric patients aged between 6 and 18 years. Patients with diagnoses confirmed using rapid antigen tests and/or RT-PCR were involved in this study.

The participants were divided into the following groups:

Group 1: Influenza A positive (n=25)

Standard symptomatic treatment + intranasal Olopatadine HCl (0.6% solution, twice daily for one week) (n=13)

Standard symptomatic treatment only (n=12)

Group 2: Influenza B positive (n=25)

Standard symptomatic treatment + intranasal Olopatadine HCl (0.6% solution, twice daily for one week) (n = 13)

Standard symptomatic treatment only (n=12)

Group 3: Influenza A and B co-infection (n=5)

Standard symptomatic treatment + intranasal Olopatadine HCl (0.6% solution, twice daily for one week) (n=3)

Standard symptomatic treatment only (n=2)

Symptoms were assessed through face-to-face interviews conducted with the patients and/or their parents after obtaining written informed consent.

The evaluated symptoms included: fever (>38°C), cough, fatigue, muscle and joint pain, sore throat, nasal congestion, and sneezing.

RESULTS

Patients who presented to the Pediatric Outpatient Clinics of Prof. Dr. Cemil Taşcıoğlu City Hospital of Health Sciences University and Yalova Training and Research Hospital and were diagnosed with influenza A/B between 1 January and 15 March 2025 were included in this study. Among the participants, 23 were male and 27 were female, with ages ranging between 6 and 18 years.

Participants were categorized into three groups, and retrospective symptom data were collected through face-to-face interviews. Information on the duration of each symptom experienced during the illness period was recorded.

Group 1: Influenza A cases (n=25)

Duration of nasal congestion: Olopatadine group: 2 days | Control group: 6 days (p < 0.001)

Duration of sneezing: Olopatadine group: 1 day | Control group: 7 days (p < 0.001)

No statistically significant difference was observed in other symptoms (Table 1, Figure 1).

Group 2: Influenza B cases (n=25)

Duration of nasal congestion: Olopatadine group: 1 day | Control group: 3 days (p < 0.01)

Duration of sneezing: Olopatadine group: 1 day | Control group: 4 days (p < 0.01)

No statistically significant difference was observed between the groups for systemic symptoms (Table 1, Figure 1).

Virus Type	Symptom	Olopatadine Group (days)	Control Group (days)	p value
Influenza A	Nasal Congestion	2	6	<0.001
Influenza A	Sneezing	1	7	<0.001
Influenza B	Nasal Congestion	1	3	<0.01
Influenza B	Sneezing	1	4	<0.01

Figure 1. Duration of Nasal Symptoms in Influenza A Cases

Group 3: Influenza A and B dual-positive cases (n=5);

Nasal congestion duration: Olopatadine group: 1 day | Control group: 6 days ($p < 0.001$)

Sneezing duration: Olopatadine group: 1 day | Control group: 5 days ($p < 0.001$)

No statistically significant differences were observed for other symptoms.

The addition of Olopatadine Hydrochloride reduced the duration of nasal congestion by 4 days in Influenza A cases and by 2 days in Influenza B cases. For the sneezing symptom, the reduction was 6 days in Influenza A and 3 days in Influenza B cases. In particular, the duration of nasal congestion was significantly shortened by 5 days, and the duration of sneezing was reduced by 4 days in cases with dual positivity for both Influenza A and B.

DISCUSSION

During influenza infection in children, nasal symptoms significantly contribute to increased transmissibility and negatively impact daily life (1, 2). Olopatadine hydrochloride (HCl) can alleviate histamine-mediated symptoms through H1 receptor blockade (4). The data obtained in this study suggest that olopatadine may also be effective in managing the nasal symptoms with viral origin.

Intranasal antihistamines, the efficacy of which was well-documented particularly for allergic rhinitis, offer rapid relief by reducing mucosal edema and nasal secretions (4, 5). In the present study, similar effects were observed in cases of Influenza A and B. However, as it lacks antiviral activity, olopatadine offers only symptomatic relief. The findings achieved in this study provide meaningful data

regarding the symptomatic management of influenza infections, which are frequently encountered in pediatric clinical practice.

Nasal symptoms are among the most disturbing aspects of influenza infection in children (1). This study revealed that intranasal olopatadine is particularly effective in reducing the duration of nasal congestion and sneezing (5). Olopatadine, a histamine H1 receptor antagonist, can rapidly suppress mucosal histamine responses when administered locally (4). Even though olopatadine does not have antiviral properties, it may reduce the duration of symptoms by alleviating mucosal edema and secretions (14).

While similar effects were well-documented in allergic rhinitis, its role in viral infections has yet to be extensively investigated in large-scale studies (2, 3, 15). The findings achieved in this study suggest that intranasal olopatadine may be a safe and effective option for the rapid control of symptoms such as nasal congestion, rhinorrhea, and sneezing, particularly in the pediatric population.

CONCLUSION

Intranasal olopatadine hydrochloride significantly reduced the duration of nasal symptoms in pediatric patients with Influenza A and B infections. It was particularly effective in alleviating symptoms such as sneezing and nasal congestion. However, it did not exhibit any marked effect on systemic symptoms.

ETHICAL DECLARATIONS

Ethics Committee Approval: This study was approved by Yalova University's Clinical Research Ethics Committee (Date: 06.01.2025, Decision No: 2025/04)

Informed Consent: Because the study was designed retrospectively, no written informed consent form was obtained from patients.

Referee Evaluation Process: Externally peer-reviewed.

Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Financial Disclosure: The authors declared that this study has received no financial support.

Author Contributions: All of the authors declare that they have all participated in the design, execution, and analysis of the paper, and that they have approved the final version.

REFERENCES

1. Eccles R. Understanding the symptoms of the common cold and influenza. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2005;5(11):718–25.
2. Skoner DP. Allergic rhinitis: definition, epidemiology, pathophysiology, detection, and diagnosis. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2001;108(1 Suppl):S2–S8.

3. Dykewicz MS, Wallace DV, Baroody F, et al. Treatment of seasonal allergic rhinitis: An evidence-based focused 2017 guideline update. *Ann Allergy Asthma Immunol.* 2017;119(6):489-511.
4. Kawauchi H, Yanai K, Wang DY, et al. Antihistamines for allergic rhinitis treatment: Is it time for new guidelines? *Allergol Int.* 2009;58(2):157-65.
5. Abelson MB, Spitalny L. Combined analysis of two studies using the conjunctival allergen challenge model to evaluate olopatadine hydrochloride, a new ophthalmic antiallergic agent with dual activity. *Am J Ophthalmol.* 1998;125(6):797-804.
6. Ohmori K, Ikemura T, Kobayashi H, Mukouyama A. Pharmacological, pharmacokinetic and clinical properties of Olopatadine Hydrochloride' (Olopatadine), an antiallergic drug. *Nippon Yakurigaku Zasshi* 2001;118(1):51-8.
7. Nakano K, Takamatsu S. (Histamine produced by macrophage and T lymphocyte: a new type of signal transducer). *Nihon yakurigaku zasshi Folia pharmacologica Japonica* 2001;118(1):15-22.
8. Shiraishi M, Hirasawa N, Oikawa S, Kobayashi Y, Ohuchi K. Analysis of histamine-producing cells at the late phase of allergic inflammation in rats. *Immunol* 2000;99(4):600-6.
9. Ikemura T, Manabe H, Sasaki Y, et al. KW-4679, an antiallergic drug, inhibits the production of inflammatory lipids in human polymorphonuclear leukocytes and guinea pig eosinophils. *Int Arch Allergy Immunol* 1996;110(1):57-63.
10. Nonaka H. Effect of KW-4679, a novel antiallergic agent, on histamine H1 receptor. *Jpn J Pharmacol* 1993;61(1):87.
11. Sasaki Y, Ikemura T, Okamura K, et al. Effect of KW-4679, a novel antiallergic drug, on histamine and leukotriene release from rat peritoneal exudates cells. *Clin Pharmacol Ther* 1995;5(1):1837-49.
12. Sharif NA, Xu SX, Yanni JM. Olopatadine (AL-4943A): ligand binding and functional studies on a novel, long acting H1-selective histamine antagonist and anti-allergic agent for use in allergic conjunctivitis. *J Ocul Pharmacol Ther.* 1996;12(4):401-7.
13. Sur DK, Scandale S. Treatment of allergic rhinitis. *Am Fam Physician.* 2010;81(12):1440-6.
14. ClinicalTrials.gov. Olopatadine Nasal Spray in the Treatment of Upper Respiratory Tract Symptoms. Identifier: NCT01266342. Updated March 15, 2022. Available at: <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT01266342>
15. Blaiss MS. Important aspects in management of allergic rhinitis: compliance, cost, and quality of life. *Allergy Asthma Proc.* 2003;24(4):231-8.